

Nollywood and Changing Trends: The Use of Visual Effects in Creating Believable Illusions.

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Abstract

One aspect of film production that is less theorised in analysis is the post production stage. This is the editing stage where the creative manipulation of computer generated images and sounds helps to fashion the overall outcome of the product. The visual effect components of films are not only created to attract attention to symbolic scenes but also made to heighten aesthetics in order to create spectacle for the viewing pleasure of audiences. This paper, which looks at the practice of editing in the Nigerian film industry, argues that the taken-for-granted nature of twisting sounds and visuals is the main reason for the much touted technical flaws in its cinematography. By means of critical analysis therefore, a purposive selection of some video-films are used to illustrate this problem so as to foreground the need for change. To analyse selected films, digital theory of editing is adopted in the assumption that these films employ continuity editing efficiently. It generally seeks for the entrenchment of expertise in the post production process of Nollywood films while challenging the guild of editors to raise the bar of their profession to an acceptable standard than leave it open in a free-for-all manner. Such a method is one way of killing the trade and at best of how not to create believable illusions for audiences.

Keywords: Editing, Aesthetics, Nollywood, Believable Illusions and Nigerian film industry.

Résumé

L'un des aspects de la production cinématographique moins théorisé dans l'analyse est l'étape de post-production. C'est la phase d'édition où la manipulation créative d'images et de sons générés par ordinateur aide à façonner le résultat global du produit. Les composants à effet visuel des films ne sont pas seulement créés pour attirer l'attention sur des scènes symboliques, mais aussi pour accentuer l'esthétique afin de créer un spectacle pour le plaisir visuel du public. Cet article, qui s'intéresse à la pratique de l'édition dans l'industrie cinématographique nigériane, affirme que la nature des sons et des visuels déformés est la principale raison des défauts techniques tant vantés dans sa cinématographie. Par conséquent, au moyen d'une analyse critique, une sélection raisonnée de certains films-vidéo est utilisée pour illustrer ce problème afin de mettre en avant le besoin de changement. Pour analyser les films sélectionnés, la théorie de l'édition numérique est adoptée dans l'hypothèse que ces films emploient efficacement l'édition de la continuité. Il cherche généralement à l'enchâssement de l'expertise dans le processus de post-production des films de Nollywood tout en remettant la guilde des éditeurs pour relever la barre de leur profession à un niveau acceptable plutôt que de la laisser ouverte de manière totalement gratuite. Une telle méthode est une façon de détruire le marché ; et au mieux, comment ne pas créer des illusions crédibles pour le public.

Mots-clés: Edition, Esthétique, Nollywood, Illusions croyables et industrie cinématographique nigériane.

Introduction

The 1985 Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in Nigeria which resulted in the high cost of living affected the cost of cinefilm production and spurred experimentations that orchestrated the production of films with video cameras. This resulted in an avalanche of video film productions, one of which was the production of *Living in Bondage* (1992) which crystallized video film industry in Nigeria. The birth of Nollywood has generated a lot of interest in academia. Before the production of the blockbuster, *Living in Bondage*, Nigerians witnessed film production of *Kongi's Harvest* in 1970 which was directed by an African American Ossie Davies (Shaka 13). Thereafter, most theatrical productions in the western part of Nigeria were adapted to films. Shaka recalls that the post SAP video film experimentations saw an avalanche of video film productions. Citing Uge, he asserts that between 1987 and 1988, Solomon Eze (Mike Orihedinma) produced video films such as *Ochoifekwu*, *Adaeze*, *The Olanna series*, *The Onyemaechi series* and *Ihe naeme series* (13). These video films were edited with the linear editing technique. Similarly, Innocent Ohiri's popular television series *Hot Cash* (willy-willy) which thrilled the viewers in the late 1980s with its vanishing visual effects was also edited with the linear editing method.

Video film as an iconographic art is an illusion of reality and highly indebted to visual effects. Based on this, editing arguably is as old as film itself. There are both linear and non-linear editing methods. Linear editing is the first type of editing that enables the synergizing of different shots to a single unbroken shot. It is referred to as a straight line editing and a method which requires the use of two or more analogue video cassette players to synthesize pictures. How this is done is that the video cassette players are connected to a mixer which serves as a link between the video cassette players and the television monitors where the working project is viewed. Unlike the linear editing method, the nonlinear style of editing enables video rushes captured to the system unit (computer) to have the flexibility of interaction with one another. This provides an editor with a limitless opportunity for the creation and manipulation of visual effects.

This aim of this paper is to critically examine the use of both visual effects and special effects in Nollywood narratives. The methodology of textual analysis is applied to some purposive selected movies from the stable of Nollywood for illustrations, such as *Igodo* and *Dog of War* and *Idemili*. While *Igodo* exemplifies the application of visual effects, *Dog of War* is used to discuss the application of special effects. Juxtaposing the editing style used in them against that of Ernest Obi's film, *Idemili*, is where critical attention is summoned in this paper in order to technically point out the roles that visual effects can play in films through mainly, the editing process. Arguably, ninety percent of Nollywood films employ continuity editing in their narratives although their effectiveness differs. Therefore, to analyze selected films, digital theory of editing is adopted in the assumption that these films employ continuity editing efficiently. This theory asserts that the efficiency of diverse effects in a narrative is attributed to CGI. Most directors in Nollywood employ the art of visual or special effects to create believable illusions in their narrative.

Film Editing and Visual Effects

Since the inception of Nollywood, the application of visual effects to beef up storylines has been very significant. This refers to the ability of an editor to introduce computer generated images and movements to screen narrative in order to sustain viewers' pleasure. In other words, a wide range of visual effects is employed in production whereby the skill of editing is employed towards creating a seamless narrative flow of events in films. Ajiwe draws a sharp contrast between special effects and visual effects in the filmmaking process to guide discussion along this line. Whereas special effects are realized on location through props, make-up and stunts during the production stage of the filmmaking process, visual effects refer to the computer generated images (CGI) applied to film narratives during the non-linear (editing) post-production stage (4). Importantly, the focus of this paper is on the application of visual effects to screen narratives during editing. Here, editing synergizes individual shots in the film to a single unbroken composition. Shots are photographed in three basic conventional sequences: *the master shot (MLS)* which is the establishing shot, the medium close up shot (MCU), and finally the close up shot (CU). The art of editing combines these shots into a single whole in order to tell a story seamlessly. Thus, by means of non-linear editing, there is the harmonization of time and space for the purpose of a unified perception. Casty observes that images and scenes from different times and places can be synergized as a single whole in unity (19). What this means is that even when two shots are taken at different locations, it is the artistry of the editor that unifies them to tell a story. If for instance, a director takes an establishment shot of a building in a particular location such as Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria and takes another interior shot in a different location such as Lagos, it is through editing that the potentials of the film are to be realized. In achieving these effects, care should be taken to ensure that they are smoothly done to avoid distractions and to make the different shots and sequences synergize as one unbroken narrative picture.

The technological revolution that characterizes film in the world lends credence to how visual effects can significantly contribute to the meaning-making process of storylines. Starting with the forerunners of film editing such as Edwin S. Porter, D.W. Griffith, Alfred Hitchcock, Sergei Eisenstein and Vsevolod Ilarionovich Pudovkin, editing is one aspect of filmmaking where creativity is made to count. If one is meant to rehearse history here, it is to say that even though film emerged in 1895 as a single shot, it has changed dramatically to include series of shots projected at the speed of twenty four frames per second during screening. Edwin S. Porter, it can be said, started the art of editing in 1903 after noticing that single shots recorded incomplete actions. His film, *The Life of American Fireman* which is made up of 20 shots tells the story of firemen who rescue a mother and child from a burning building. Using newsreel footage of a real fire and performed interiors, Porter presents a six—minutes story of the victims and their rescuers. This film shows how the mother and child are saved (Dancyger 4). Leaning on the power of editing and visual effects, he produced *The Great Train Robbery* too which is twelve minutes in length with fourteen shots. The narrative tells the story of train robbery and the subsequent fate of the robbers. This was an improvement on what he did previously having acquired more sophisticated editing techniques. Following him is D.W. Griffith who advanced the

technique of editing by achieving shot clarity through his grasping of the full range of dramatic construction.

D. W. Griffith is one man who introduced shot variations such as: extreme long shots, close up shots, cutaway shots and tracking shots in the early days of filmmaking in human history. This kind of shots arguably came to form the bedrock of modern film editing known as the master scene technique. Some of his films include *The Greaser's Gauntlet* (1908), *Enoch Arden* (1908), *The Birth of a Nation* (1915) (Dancyger 18). On the other hand, Sergei Eisenstein a Russian filmmaker, director and academic, developed the editing theory known as the montage technique. He anchored this style of film editing on the impact of Griffith's films on viewers. Following his theatrical background as a designer, Eisenstein theorised film editing as a clash of images and ideas. This, he demonstrates with his film, *Strike* (1924) by emphasising its five components: metric, rhythmic, tonal, over tonal and intellectual montages. (Dancyger 18). His technique sees a single filmic shot as meaningless prior to its placement within the montage structure. Thus, a shot gains meaning relationally as part of a large system when synergized with other shots (Stam 38).

Like those before him, Alfred Hitchcock advances the art of editing by pushing its boundaries. Stam, in describing his style, notes that Hitchcock believes that meaning can be generated less through expressive performance of the actors than through the manipulation of performance through editing (39). He thus experimented on various types of visual effects in editing. His film, *The Bird* (1963), was a notable attempt at the manipulation of visual effects with the animation of birds on revenge to humanity (Dancyger, 99). Pudovkin, on his own is notable for his concept of *spatio-temporal* continuity by means of editing. By this is meant, the placement of camera in relation to dramatic elements to ensure visual composition that will guide the viewers' physical psychology through the narrative. Stam notes that Pudovkin believes that the key to cinema looks lies in organizing and managing the perception and feelings of the spectator through editing and staging (39). His editing techniques include: *contrast*, *parallelism*, *simultaneity*, *leitmotif* and *symbolism*. In his contrast editing theory, the editor establishes a dramatic concept and places another dramatic action in an alternating scenario. For instance, the story of a hungry man will make more impact to the viewer's psychology if juxtaposed with that of a senseless well-to-do glutton that wastes food. In parallelism, he notes that it is similar to contrast. Here he observes that two dramatic actions propel the narrative with a time frame heightening the sequence to a conflict. In symbolism, he discusses the sign representation of dramatic actions. A shot of a hangman murdering a man could be juxtaposed with a shot of a bull slaughter in a stockyard. In simultaneity, he explains that two actions propel the dramatic conflict with the outcome of one influencing the outcome of the other. Finally, he observes that in leitmotif, emphasis on the basic theme is being reiterated (Pudovkin 77-78).

Similarly Eisenstein notes that shot and montage are the basic elements of film (104). Montage is therefore an arrangement of shots in sequence to achieve visual narrative effect. Eisenstein agrees with Pudovkin that montage is the means of unrolling an idea with the help of single shots and opines that montage is an idea that arises from the collision of independent shots: shot even opposite to one another. Pudovkin's studies on editing gives a broad view on the visual impression of film editing. He asserts that editing can be applied for special visual narrative effects. According to him, "editing is one of the most significant

instruments of effects possessed by film technicians and theatre, by the scenarist also” (Pudovkin 77).

It is worth noting that though the classical *cut* technique from *master shot* to *close up* is still apt in the modern films, the evolutionary theories of editing have drastically affected the modern editing techniques. However the digital theory which anchors its principles on the modern technological advancement most times reverses the classical *shot* trend from *close-up* to *master shot*. The theories of inductive and deductive screen approaches are part of such digital theories. Inductive screen technique is revolution against the classical editing techniques of scene revelation from *mastershot* to *close up shot*. This occurs where viewers are inductively let into a scenic action through the emotional development of the selected close-up shots. This is unlike the deductive screen approach which obeys the classical editing rules of revealing a scene from the *master shot* to a *close up shot*. Yet these digital theories do not ignore continuity theories. Rather it can be said that the new media is all inclusive. It embraces different classical theories of editing and combines them with modern approach which is driven by some form of technological revolution. Citing Walter Benjamin’s seminal essay, Henry Jenkins asserts that;

Digital theory may address anything from the role of CGI special effects in Hollywood blockbusters to new systems of communication; the net, new genres of entertainment; the computer game, new styles of representation; digital photography or virtual reality (Stam, 318).

Stam noted that the digital era influence by the internet, computer game, and virtual reality has its impact in the new method of film narrative. This has transformed different film theories such as Auteurism, Apparatus Theory, Spectatorship, Realize Aesthetics;

Digital imaging also leads to the de-ontologization of the Bazinian image. With the dominance of digital image production, where virtually any image becomes possible, the connection of images to solid substance has become tenuous... images are no longer guaranteed as visual truth. The artist need no longer search for a pro-filmic model in the world; one can give visible form to abstract ideas and improbable dream (319).

Stam equally notes that viewers’ knowledge of simulation makes them skeptical about the image’s true value. The digital theory has achieved so much visual revolutions on the screen.

One aspect of digital theory is the virtual reality. This implies the stimulation of illusion to achieve corporality. One of the scholars who have studied virtual reality in Nigeria is Orisaremi. According to him, *Virtual Reality* (VR) is applied by different professions such as Architecture, Engineering for different purposes. However, its creative and utility impacts for artistes are more effective than these other professions (100). Citing Mark Reaney, a research fellow of virtual reality, he likened virtual reality to the theatrical fourth wall and posits that theatre is the original VR machine in which a viewer visits an imaginary world that is both immersive and interactive even before the design of most powerful computers (107). Nollywood films equally employ the use of both special and visual effects in its narratives. Thus an overview of these concepts suffice the purposively selected films for analyses.

A Critique of Believable Illusions in Nollywood

In *Dog of War*, Uzee Madubogwu uses special effect of dog as a character in the film whereas in *Igodo*, *Egg of Life*, *House on Fire*, *Suicide Mission* to mention a few, the directors of these films applied the use of visual effects to realize believable illusions in the narratives. One director who combines both special and visual effects in his films is Ernest Obi. However, *Living in Bondage*, a film which most scholars agree launched Nollywood had a feel of visual effects. The appearance of Merit's ghost to hunt Andy the major character of the narrative lends credence to this assertion. Andy had used Merit his wife for money ritual and Merit's ghost is stimulated to hunt him thereafter. It should be noted that *Living in Bondage's* stimulation of Merit's ghost is done with special effects and edited through linear editing method, therefore the appearance and disappearance of her image is mechanical. Apart from *Living in Bondage*, other films that emerged thereafter have advanced in their application of visual and special effects. For instance, films such as *House on Fire*(1998), *Igodo* (1999), *Egg of Life*(2000),*Pestilence*(2002), *Suicide Mission*(1999), *Dog of War*(2007), *Odum Na Ogbu Agu*(2007)have stunning visual effects. Most recently, *Idemili* (2014), directed by Ernest Obi has stunning visual effects that evoke serious fear and suspense among teeming viewers.

Igodo, an epic film which throws light on communal sacrifice is one of the greatest epic video film genres that emerged in Nollywood from the staple of OJ productions in 1999. Directed by Andy Amanechi, Iheukwumere being a victim of men's conspiracy is buried alive. A crime committed by seven men spell calamity and breeds death amongst the people of Umuoka. A spiritual tree must be cut with a spiritual knife from the shrine of Amadioha far away in the evil forest. Since the crime was committed by seven men, seven young men are beckoned to go to the evil forest and fetch the spiritual cutlass. Thus seven men embark on an expedition in the land of the dead in quest of Amadioha's spiritual knife. Only *Igodo* returns with the spiritual knife. There in the evil forest, they are hunted by various ghosts. The ghost's appearance and disappearance are realized through visual effects. These were realized through nonlinear editing methods and thus these effects are sophisticated and evoke fear that enables willing suspension of disbelief. There is the essential use of sound effects to herald the appearance of a ghost or danger in the evil forest. Deductive visual approach is mostly used and shot compositions are technically handled to drive home the narrative.

On the other hand, *Suicide Mission*, one of the ritual video films that emerged in 1998, directed by Fred Amata revolves around Austin's family. Monique (Regina Askia) being madly infatuated by Austin who is already married with three kids, goes to the herbalist for magical charm that will make Austin marry her. After consulting the first herbalist whose charm lacks potency, she proceeds to the second herbalist and following her desperation, makes love to the spirit of a dead man as required by the herbalist. Austin's effigy is then given to Monique in a bottle. She is thus advised never to allow the bottle to break. Consequently, Austin marries Monique and sends his wife parking following Monique's setup. Monique later decides to kill Austin and inherit his wealth. She goes back to the herbalist who prepares a charm for her. On her way back, the charm is beaten by rain contrary to the herbalist's earlier warning that water should not touch the charm. Consequently she runs mad. Being mad, Austin gets a pastor who prays for her. After

confessing, Monique mistakenly breaks the bottle containing Austin's effigy and finally turns into a dog. The stimulation of Austin's image in a bottle through CGI is very commendable. This makes the film evoke the required fear, tension and surprise needed to make it successful.

Figure 1. Visual effect of Austin's effigy (Richard Mofe Damijo) in a bottle.

Furthermore *Dog of War* is a tragic video film that revolves around the character of a Dog: called Uli. Following Mezie Mmadu's death, his kinsmen gather to hear his will and dissatisfied that only an average of five million naira was willed to them from Mmadu's multi billion naira estate, they decide to kill his only son Ken who has just returned from abroad for the burial ceremony. Nathy, the late Mezie Mmadu's gardener who is also willed the sum of five million naira continues his duties diligently in Mezie Mmadu's house. While working, his daughter Rose brings him food on a particular day. Citing and admiring her, Ken sends Uli (his dog) a message to her in a piece of paper. Ken and Rose finally meet and fall in love. Different plots by Ken's uncles to kill him are flawed by Uli's (dog) semiotic language.

His uncles, led by Oba Ejike invite Ken for a family meeting in the process of which they poisoned his drink. Ken is distracted by Uli (dog) from taking the poisoned drink. On another occasion, Oba Ejike equally poisons his drink, this is also foiled by Uli. Further attempts to take Ken's life are thwarted by Uli. Oba Ejike's hired assassins could not find Ken because Uli tells him of the impending doom. Oba Ejike further engages Udoka to kill Ken with food poison. Uli throws the food away. The second attempt through food poisoning by Ejike takes the filmic action to a climax as Ken ignoring Uli's warnings eats the poisoned food. Following this, he dies instantly. Uli takes to revenge and kills Ken's uncles for killing Ken.

Figure 2. Ken being distracted by Uli not to take a poisoned drink in Dog of War

Figure 3. Uli sends a letter to Rose.

The narrative centring on the character Uli, a Rottweiler dog, is marked with great semiotic components which were realized through special effects. There is high level of sign language between the central character Uli and other actors in the narrative film. The extension of the semiotic language of the dog's character in relation to human character propels the narrative to a climatic state where Ken's flaw in failing to decode Uli's signs leads to his (Ken) death.

The special effects which are realized through the activities of the dog is very

impressive. Uli is used comprehensively in the narrative as seen in his tamed behaviour. He delivers letters from Ken to Rose and vice versa. This function becomes intensified when Rose's father, Nathy, afraid of being branded a gold-digger, confines his daughter Rose to house arrest to prevent her from seeing Ken. Uli's character is properly defined and remains consistent throughout the narrative. The aesthetics of the film's special effects lies on Uli, the central character who is used to resolve the dramatic conflict. Uli, a tragic character fights the killers of his master Ken.

Finally *Idemili* a narrative that combines special and visual effects in equal measures is the major focus of this paper. *Idemili* an epic film tells the story of the princess of Idemili. Being a princess of Idemili, the law forbids her to fall in love, much more to marry. However, contrary to this tradition, she falls in love with Okwadike her betrothed. Egbeigwe the chief priest objects the relationship between Okwadike and Ekemma. He immediately takes Ekemma on her initiation to priesthood rights. As Ekemma embarks on her priestly initiation, Okwadike goes to rescue her from the initiation which he (Okwadike) claims was against her wish. At the point of rescue, he and his men are struck dead as they tried to liberate the hypnotized Ekemma. Ekemma who is believed to be carrying the burden of the nine villages of Ebenato regains her consciousness as Okwadike dies. She begs Egbeigwe the chief priest to resuscitate Okwadike. As Egbeigwe tells her that Okwadike has died, Ekemma runs out of the village without completing her initiation rites. The effect of Ekemma's disappearance sets the filmic conflict in motion.

In the modern day, another Ekemma, the granddaughter of the pre-modern Ekemma emerges. She is to be married to a prince. As they are to consummate their love, Ekemma is tied by a python symbolizing the spirit of idemili. Therefore oblivious of her past, Ekemma goes to retrace it while the people arrange a purported virgin for the prince to marry in place of Ekemma. The tradition of the land stipulates that only a virgin marries the Prince. Thus after making love to the purported virgin, the prince's genital organ turns to a female genital organ. For the genital organ to be reversed to that of a man, the prince must bring Ekemma who is the priestess of Idemili. The prince thus goes in search of Ekemma who had embarked on an expedition to discover her past.

Idemili, is an engaging narrative. It is filled with poetic diction which makes the lucidity of the narrative. The English transliteration of Igbo language is apt in the narrative. This enhances its epic outlook. Obi employs the concept of referral story device, a technique where a particular story begets another in succession. Thus, he told many stories and was able to sustain the interest of the viewers with his visual effects. His characters are properly developed, and remain consistent all through the narrative. Thus, he achieved causality with his proper delineation of different characters. However, this film is replete with the traditional elongations of actions seen in most Nollywood films. This was covered this with various effects. His dramatic blocking of actors on set creates an effect of the inclusive and communal nature of African society. He employs deep Igbo cultural symbols in his dramatic construct. The concept of achieving a sacrifice at the cross road of three parts is seen in this film. The incantations of various chief priests has semblance to real situation and are not as fictions as we see in most Nollywood films.

On his believable illusions, Ernest Obi's *Idemili* is effectively realized through digital theory of editing. Obi employs inductive shot techniques to evoke fear on his

viewers. This he combined with creative sound cues that depict the mood. Obi's filmic mood is deepened within his set construct which are exotic and expressive and his use of music which depicts the ritualistic nature of Igbo culture. Unlike most Nollywood narratives which have bias on either special or visual effects, Ernest Obi combines both in equal measures. This makes his films exceptional in believable illusions. For instance in examining his special effects, this paper strongly argues that the python that the pre-modern Ekemma ties on her neck is a real python. The behavioural attributes of the python apparently disproves any argument in favour of a rubber python. Of course, the director in an interview will often not reveal his special effect secret. On the other hand, in his visual effects, he adopts the concept of shocking stimulations to send across his message. First, at the inception of the film, the modern Ekemma is seen pursued by three spiritual birds. The birds are visually stimulated. Thereafter, there are avalanche of effects during the preparation stages of the pre-modern Ekemma's initiation to priesthood. This climaxed as Okwadike tries to rescue her in her initiation process.

Some of the noticeable effects therein are: Ekemma's eyes that change to various colours during some of the ritual practices in the film. In addition water splashes from Ekemma's feet as she runs during her tribulations in the film. This is followed by cloudy screen in most scenes of the narrative where metaphysical presence is presumed. Furthermore, the vomiting of an egg by the spirit of Idemili and swallowing of the same egg by Ekemma has stunning visual effects. Moreover the roasting and subsequent death and disappearance of Okwadike's friends as they come to rescue Ekemma was equally very effective. Then in subsequent seasons, some other noticeable effects are: As modern Ekemma's waist bead is cut off, smoke emits from the floor. Then the tying by a python of modern Ekemma's body shortly before she meets the prince. She is also lifted up and sustained in the air until the appeasement Idemili spirit takes place. Afterwards, the disappearance of the cup that was used to appease Idemili spirit was equally seamless. Besides, the changing colours in the eyes of modern chief priest were visually astonishing. Thus the appearance of the three ancestors from the wall, the splash of light as the dibia clampedS hand and the emission of fire from his mouth were all intriguing. There are also various ritualistic activities and incarnations in the narrative. These came with their various visual effects.

Conclusion

By means of critical analysis of some purposive selected video-films, this paper used digital theory of editing to delineate the differences and similarities in the use of special and visual effect by some film directors. It hopes to entrench expertise in the post production process of Nollywood films while challenging the guild of editors to raise the bar of their profession to an acceptable standard than leave it open in a free-for-all manner. There has been steady growth in Nollywood since its inception. Film editing has always articulated diverse shots and dramatic blocks of the narrative. However, the digital theory of editing which explores the unsurpassable roles of visual effects adds value to the narrative construct. With the domestication of this theory, it is hoped that Nollywood films will soon become number one in the world.

Works Cited

- Ajiwe, Uche. "Visual Effects in Nollywood", A PhD seminar paper presented to the School of Graduate Studies, Department of Theatre Arts, University of Port Harcourt. January 2015
- Casty, Alan. *The Dramatic Art of the film*. New York: Harper and Row publishers. 1971.
- Dancyger, ken. *The Technique of film and Video Editing; History, theory and practice*. (4ed) Oxford Focal Press, 2007.
- Eisenstein, Sergei. "From film form; the cinematographic principle and the Ideogram", in G. Mast and M. Cohen (Ed). *Film theory and Criticism* (2nd Ed.) pp.85-122. Oxford: Oxford press inc. 1979.
- Orisaremi, Alphonsus. Virtual reality in Nigeria: A study of the African independent television project. *The crab: Journal of theatre and media arts*. 1(1): pp. 105-114. 2005.
- Shaka, Femi. "History, genre and texts of the emergent video film industry in Nigeria. *Kiabara: Journal of humanities*. 8(1): Pp. 11-30. 2002.
- Podovkin, Vsevolod. "From film technique: On editing", in G. Mast and M. Cohen (Ed). *Film theory and Criticism* (2nd Ed.) Pp. 77-84. Oxford: Oxford press inc. 1978.
- Stam, Robert. *Film Theory; An introduction*. Massachusetts; Blackwell publisher Inc, 2000.
- Zetl .Herbert. *Sight, sound motion*. {4th Ed. }. Belmont:Thompson learning academic resources centre. 2005.

Videography

- Suicide Mission* (1998) Director- Fred Amata with Richard Mofe Damijo, Regina Asikia, Ameze Imorhiaghe, Obot Etuk.
- Igodo* (1999) Directors- Andy Amenechi and Don Pedro Obaseki. with Pete Edoche, Norbort Young, Sam Dede, Charles Okafor, Obi Mmadubugwu, Chidi Mokeme, Price Jome Uche, Ignis Ekwe, Joe Iyode.
- Dog of War* (2008) Director-Uzee Madubogwu, with Desmond Elliot, Ini Edo, Enebeli Elebuwa, Patience Ozorkwo, McDonald Oti.